

26 September 2025

Press release

On 25 September 2025, the CST4ALL project hosted the side event “EU CST Projects & Research Agenda” at the SolarPACES 2025 Conference in Almeria, Spain. This hybrid event, organized by DLR with contributions from all project partners, had over 70 in-person and remote participants, including representatives from the European Commission, national authorities, industry, associations, engineering and consultancy firms, research institutions and universities.

Daniel Benitez (DLR) opened the event with an overview of ongoing EU-funded CST projects which are addressing the seven priority areas of the CST Implementation Plan in the SET Plan, from line-focus and central receiver technologies to thermal storage, solar fuels and cross-cutting applications.

The event featured a series of presentations from selected projects, namely [MSA-Trough](#), [ASTERIX-CAESar](#), [Sun-to-Liquid II](#), [SolarSCO2OL](#), [SHARP-sCO2](#), [SALTOPower](#), and [HySelect](#), focusing on their objectives, outcomes, impacts, and future outlook. Key takeaways from the project presentations include the following:

- The projects are advancing technologies for power generation, industrial process heat and solar fuels, highlighting the role of CST beyond electricity.
- Strong emphasis is on combining CST with other technologies (e.g., PV, electrical heaters, sCO₂ cycles) to improve flexibility, efficiency and costs.
- Several demonstration projects aim to bring CST closer to market deployment with pilot plants already planned.
- Projects also strengthen EU research infrastructures, international cooperation and engagement with early-stage researchers.

The workshop concluded with an engaging roundtable discussion on CST funding frameworks and future funding requirements, moderated by Ricardo Sanchez Moreno (CIEMAT), with Marina Montero Carrero (European Commission, DG RTD), Clara Astudillo Llorente (CINEA), Cristina Trueba Alonso (CST IWG Chair) and María Luisa Revilla Trujillo (CDTI) participating in the panel. The discussion focused on the following points:

- Horizon Europe currently offers fewer CST-specific calls, as the trend is shifting towards more open and less descriptive calls for industrial decarbonization and clean tech manufacturing under the Clean Industrial Deal.
- The upcoming Innovation Fund heat auction is a major funding opportunity for flagship projects within the scope of CST.
- The European Commission is expanding lump sum funding to simplify project management and encourage more industry players to participate and coordinate projects.
- The Clean Energy Transition Partnership is a key mechanism to align national, regional and European research agendas.

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the European Union**

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CST4ALL Coordinator

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CST4ALL Partners

CIEMAT: Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas, Medioambientales y Tecnologicas (ES)

ITALIAN NATIONAL AGENCY FOR NEW TECHNOLOGIES,
ENERGY AND SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile (IT)

ESTELA: European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (BE)

GUNAM: Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications (TR)

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